

6.5: Manual to the Eco-design tool

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	814505
Project Full Title	Recycling of coated and painted textile and plastic materials
Project Acronym	DECOAT
Funding scheme	RIA
Start date of the project	January 1 st , 2019
Duration	54 months
Project Coordinator	Guy Buyle (CTB)
Project Website	http://decoat.eu/project/

Deliverable Information

Deliverable n°	6.5
Deliverable title	Manual for the Eco-design tool v1 (qualitative)
WP no.	6
WP Leader	IRES
Contributing Partners	EM, all
Nature	CO
Authors	Brienne Wiersema (EM), Natalia Chebaeva (EM), Maria Papavasileiou (EM)
Contributors	EM
Reviewers	Elias Koumoulos (IRES)
Contractual Deadline	M54 (postponed due to Covid-19)
Delivery date to EC	

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (incl. Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (incl. Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for the members of the consortium (incl. Commission Services)	

Document Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
0.1	05.07.2023	Brienne Wiersema (EM), Natalia Chebaeva (EM)	First draft

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1 Goal and scope of DECOAT.....	3
1.2 Goal and scope of the Eco-design tool.....	3
1.3 Setup of the tool	3
2. Eco-Design tool: User Manual.....	4
Annex A: Tool Development.....	10
2.1 Eco-design tool concept	10
2.2 Defining relevant inputs and outputs	10
2.3 Conceptual architecture of the tool.....	10
2.4 Development process	10
2.5 Alfa version – qualitative tool.....	11
2.6 Beta version – publicly available tool	11
2.6.1. Online tool.....	11
2.6.2. Offline tool	12
Annex B: Methodology.....	13

1. Introduction

1.1 Goal and scope of DECOAT

The main goal of DECOAT is to enable the circular use of textiles and plastic parts with (multilayer) coatings, which are typically not yet recyclable. These coatings comprise functional and/or aesthetical coatings or paints, possibly combined with adhesion layers/primers. Therefore, novel triggerable polymer material systems and the corresponding recycling processes are developed. The triggerable solutions are based on smart additives (like microcapsules or microwave triggered additives) for the coating formulations, activated by a specific trigger (heat, humidity, microwave, chemical), or detachment technologies facilitating separation of coating from the substrate at the end-of-life.

1.2 Goal and scope of the Eco-design tool

The eco-design tool aims at supporting the industrial sectors in identifying eco-design strategies for new products, specifically in regards of coated plastics and textiles. The current version (alfa 1) is the first version of the tool to be released, which aims at serving the industrial partners within the project with a qualitative assessment of the DECOAT solutions.

The tool inquires a set of datapoints about the product in question, matches it with the developed DECOAT solutions, and provides a qualitative assessment of the match together with information on environmental, social, and economic benefits.

1.3 Setup of the tool

Fig. 1: Schematic overview of the tool back-end.

The back-end of the tool is designed to match the user-input on the preferred substrate, coating and product performance with a matrix that contains all types of information on the technical aspects of the DECOAT solution. Based on the combination of these two datapoints (the matrix and the user-input), an advice is generated suggesting which DECOAT solution is most suitable and appropriate for the user needs, as well as some technical background on the pros and cons of both solutions. Finally, the eco-design advice is generated and provided for the matched solutions. It entails information on the compatibility with the product performance, the environmental performance, circularity, business opportunities and safety.

2. Eco-Design tool: User Manual

In this chapter, a step by step walk through of the Eco-design tool is provided and supported with screenshots illustrating examples of the model.

Disclaimer!: Please note that the tool is intended to provide only the first impressions of the solutions developed within the DECOAT projects, and is makes a wide use of the generic information and assumptions. The information of the tool cannot be used for any claims, does not substitute a product-specific analyses, and shall be taken with the perspective of the "first idea" to be taken into further consideration. The DECOAT consortium in general, and the developers of the solutions and the tool in particular, cannot be held liable for any information provided, nor for the use of it by third parties for any design, engineering, or communication and marketing processes.

DECOAT Goals and objectives
The main goal of DECOAT is to enable the circular use of textiles and plastic parts with (multilayer) 'coatings', which are typically not recyclable yet. These 'coatings' comprise of functional and performance coatings and paints, as well as adhesion layers. Two main ideas are explored in the project: dissolution of a coating system from the substrate, and introducing a triggerable primer to the coating system that can be activated at the end of life, causing separation of the coating and substrate.

[Read more about the project at www.decoat.eu](http://www.decoat.eu)

Main DECOAT concept

DECOAT is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 814505

EcoDesign tool - Goals and objectives
The main goal of the EcoDesign tool is to support industrial players in identifying opportunities related to application of the solutions developed in the DECOAT project. The tool considers the aspects related to the ecodesign of the product, including compatibility, circularity, safety, environmental and economic performance.

EcoDesign tool - How it works
In the tool, there are three topics where input is required: Product and performance, Substrate and coating and the End-of-life scenario and waste treatment. If you would like to look at the Eco-design advice for multiple options, please fill in the tool several times. In order for the tool to function, it is important to adjust all input areas per run of the tool. You can navigate between the topics by clicking the buttons on top of the screen. To start, you can click the start-button.

Disclaimer
Please note that the tool is intended to provide only the first impressions of the solutions developed within the DECOAT projects, and is makes a wide use of the generic information and assumptions. The information of the tool cannot be used for any claims, does not substitute a product-specific analyses, and shall be taken with the perspective of the "first idea" to be taken into further consideration. The DECOAT consortium in general, and the developers of the solutions and the tool in particular, cannot be held liable for any information provided, nor for the use of it by third parties for any design, engineering, or communication and marketing processes.

Start

© Copyright by the DECOAT Consortium, 2023

Fig. 2: Introduction page of the Eco-design tool.

To navigate through the tool, you can use the navigation pane at the top. For all categories, you will be asked to answer a couple of questions that are either multiple choice or yes/no questions. The questions are related to the following topics: the product and performance, coating and preferred end-of-life scenario. **It is important that, for every run with the tool, you start from the first question and proceed to answer all following questions.**

In the tab "Product and performance", fill in the information about the applied industry, type of substrate, total weight of the coated product in kg, total weight of uncoated product in kg, and the importance of the smooth feel of the product.

In this tab, data is collected on the product and the performance of the product during its lifetime. The product performance indicators focus on external factors that influence the product during its lifetime, and on essential aspects of the product aesthetics, such as the feel and flexibility of textiles and the feel and the strenght of plastic parts. Please select an answer in all grey boxes, and check all product performance indicators that are relevant to the performance of your product

In case you change grey boxes in the on the industry:

In what industry is your organization active?	
Of what type of substrate is the product made?	
What is the total weight of the product?	Kilograms (kg)
What is the weight of the uncoated product?	Kilograms (kg)
Is smooth feel essential for your product?	

Fig. 3: Product and performance input sheet

Note:

- Different industries have different materials available. If you decide to change the industry filled in, please make sure that the chosen material of a substrate or coating are applicable in the newly chosen industry
- When filling in the mass of coated and uncoated product, make sure that the mass of the coated product is higher than the mass of the uncoated product, and both values are positive numbers.

In the tab **“Coating”** fill in the information about the solvent base of the coating, polymer base of the coating, and the surface area for coating.

In this tab, data is collected on the type of coating and binders that are applied on the substrate. Please select an answer in all grey boxes. If you change the industry in the tab “Product and Performance”, remember to change the answers in this tab as well.

What coating base is currently used on the product?	
What coating is currently used on the product?	
What is the coated surface of the product?	Square meters (m2)

Fig. 4: Coating input sheet

In the tab **“End of life and Waste”** fill in the information about the planned end of life: post-consumer or post-industrial. Note, post-industrial waste assumed recovery of the defect or unsold products, while post-consumer waste assumer recovery after use of the product by final user. In case of the post-industrial waste recovery, please fill in information about the assumed locations and outsourcing of the processes. Optionally, you can fill in the value of the recovered substrate for your situation or for the market.

In this tab, data is collected on the type of waste that is produced, and the intended use of the recycled substrate. Please select an answer in all grey boxes. If you change the industry in the tab “Product and Performance”, remember to change the answers in this tab as well.

Is it intended to use the debonding solution on post-consumer or post-industrial waste?	Post-industrial waste
Would you prefer to have debonding on the own production premises, or you would outsource it to the technology owner?	
Optional: indicate the assumed value of the recovered substrate, €/kg	

Fig. 5: End of life and Waste input sheet

After you have answered all of the data collection questions in the tool, you can proceed to the results page. Here, you will find a summary of the Eco-design advice, containing the advised DECOAT solution with a short explanation on the different solutions. Clicking on the button “Show me the alternative”, you can see an alternative solution for the case, and how it performs.

Fig. 6: Eco-design summary page, navigation to detailed pages.

At the same page you can find the overall score assigned to the solution’s application for the case, and a score for the different Eco-design dimensions that have been included in the tool. These are: Technical Compatibility, Environmental performance, Circularity & Materials, Business & Economic Risks and Safety.

You can also check how the solution would perform if one uses renewable energy in production, or/and in debonding and recycling processes, as well as if downcycling is considered at the end of life instead of recycling.

For each of the five eco-design dimensions, there is a separate page providing in-depth information regarding the suggested DECOAT solutions in combination with the answers provided in the tool by the user. You can navigate to these pages by using the navigation pane, or by clicking on the category icons.

At each of the pages, the scoring, performance, and additional information is provided. Please, note that you cannot change or input any information on these pages.

Fig. 7: Compatibility scores in the Eco-design tool.

Fig. 8: Environmental performance in the Eco-design tool.

D6.5: Manual to the Eco-design tool v1 (qualitative)

Fig. 9: Circularity score in the Eco-design tool.

Fig. 10: Business score of Eco-design tool.

Fig. 11: Chemical safety in the Eco-design tool.

For more information, or further questions on the Eco-design tool, please contact Natalia Chebaeva (natalia.chebaeva@ecomatters.nl)

Annex A: Tool Development

The current version of the eco-design tool has been developed with the vast inputs from research and industrial partners. The following main steps were conducted to reach the highest relevance of the descriptions addressing solutions, their applicability, characteristics, and performance.

2.1 Eco-design tool concept

Initially, the concept of the tool has been developed by Ecomatters B.V in the frame of Task 6.5. The tool is intended for professional use, focusing on several data categories and offering eco-design advice to the user. It was further conceptualised to connect several data inputs from the user (simple multiple-choice questions), connecting the profile of the application to a particular DECOAT solution, and then providing the relevant information for such solution.

2.2 Defining relevant inputs and outputs

To shape the in- and outputs of the tool in a way that is understandable, experienced DECOAT partners have taken part in a specifically designed survey, followed by a multilateral workshop. The participants of the survey represented waste treatment, coatings manufacturer and product manufacturer (textile/plastics). The survey addressed, in particular, Eco-design in the company (insights into the practice of sustainability assessment and use of eco-design tools), Eco-design tool's functionality (what would be expected/wanted from the tool to be delivered), and Eco-design tool's interface (the user interface requirements to the tool). In a follow-up workshop, the partners clarified and refined the conclusions of the survey, and ultimately formed the input and output points of the future tool.

As a result, the user interface mainly focusses on users upstream of the product use (manufacturers). Moreover, it has been agreed to opt for simplicity of inputs and outputs for more flexible navigation rather than elaborate analysis. The defined categories of input datapoints were detailed regarding technology, but categorical regarding the market, use, and end-of-life. Finally, the defined categories of outputs were: applicability of DECOAT solutions, benefits, changes in performance, end of life of products, and regulatory aspects.

2.3 Conceptual architecture of the tool

Following the conceptual design, the principal architecture of the tool was decided upon. The survey and the follow-up workshop are an additional help in forming the user interface features relevant for the tool architecture. Based on the work performed and decisions made in WP2, several principal DECOAT solutions are taken into further development. For these solutions, a matrix of input focal points is developed as a solutions-base of the Eco-design tool. The solution suitable for a case is defined with navigational questions. When the match is made, the most suitable solution is defined. The eco-design advice is retrieved based on the defined optimal solution in combination with user-specific inputs.

2.4 Development process

The tool development has been decided to conduct in two step:

1. alfa version of the tool, for supporting the partners of the project in decision making, and testing the conceptual architecture. The version bore a qualitative character, and based the eco-design recommendation on the general information about the solutions known at the moment of the version development
2. Beta version of the tool, available for general public and serving as the guiding tool for identification of the possible benefits and challenges of applying DECOAT solutions to the considered systems. The tool

2.5 Alfa version – qualitative tool

The alfa version of the tool was developed in the spreadsheet format (on the base of MS excel). The matrix has been implemented according to the architectural concept. Five dimensions of eco-design were considered in qualitative terms:

- Compatibility of the solutions
- Environmental performance
- Business and Economics
- Circularity
- Chemical safety

Research and industrial partners of the project were asked to populate the tool with information. The request was sent in matrix form, where each of the partners had an opportunity to provide the data available to them. Follow up meetings and written communication resolved all discrepancies and unclarities.

A simple scoring of the solutions was tested, rating each of the eco-design dimension from 1 to 5. Scoring was assigned qualitatively based on expert judgement of the DECOAT partners involved in the respective assessments. The overall score was calculated as a simple average of the scores in the eco-design dimensions.

The draft version of the tool was sent out to the research and industrial partners for validating the technical and categorical information provided, as well as for providing feedback on usability of the tool and user interface. The complete feedback was collected in written form during four bilateral meetings. The feedback was then implemented to release the alfa version of the tool presented.

The tool is available for internal use by the partners of the DECOAT project.

2.6 Beta version – publicly available tool

The beta version of the tool has been split into two parts: indicative online tool for identification of compatible DECOAT solutions, and downloadable offline tool for more detailed assessment.

2.6.1. Online tool

The online tool is an identificatory of applicable DECOAT solutions, and is based on the compatibility matrix tested in the alfa version and updated within the validation sessions with the technology developers and experts in the project Work Package 5.

The tool requests an input of industry, substrate and coating type from the user, and provides an advice on possibilities of application of two of the DECOAT solutions, taking into account compatibility tested or expected.

The identifier is hosted at ecomatters' server and is accessible at:

- DECOAT website <https://decoat.eu/>
- Ecomatters website <https://www.ecomatters.nl/decoat-eco-design-tool/>

The online tool is followed up by a downloadable excel annex with more quantitative outline and more defined advice per solution.

2.6.2. Offline tool

The downloadable tool asks for the user input on the industry, product and performance (including the weight), coating (including coated surface area) and end-of-life assumptions.

The offline tool builds up on the spreadsheet platform of the alfa version (MS Excel based), taking forward the development of the DECOAT project and the assessments performed within.

The same five dimensions are taken into the eco-design assessment:

- Compatibility
- Environmental performance
- Circularity & materials
- Business and economics
- Safety

The overall score is calculated as the weighted average of the scores in the five eco-design dimensions.

The draft version of the tool was first tested and validated internally by the developer (Ecomatters), and upon implementation of the corrections, sent out to the research and industrial partners of DECOAT for providing feedback on usability of the tool and user interface. The feedback was then implemented to release the beta version of the tool presented.

For more information on the development process, please inquire to Natalia.chebaeva[at]ecomatters.nl

Annex B: Methodology

Compatibility assessment

Compatibility assessment utilises the updated compatibility matrix (analysis performed within the Work package 2 and Work package 5). The compatibility score is defined as follows:

Score 5: the solution is experimentally proven to be compatible with the combination of substrate and coating

Score 4: the combination has not been experimentally tested, but is expected to be compatible with reasonable certainty due to proximity to the tested combinations

Score 3: the combination is principally compatible, but there are certain limitations to the applicability of the solution

Score 2: the combination has not been tested, there are no informed assumption on compatibility

Score 1: the combination has been tested and proved to be not compatible

Environmental performance

Environmental performance of the solutions is based on a simplified life cycle analysis, and makes use of the characterisation methods developed by the Joint Research Centre in frames of the EF method development. The method allows to calculate the impacts in 16 impact categories, and aggregate them in a single score through normalisation and weighting. More about the EF method is available on https://green-business.ec.europa.eu/environmental-footprint-methods_en. Important: the study does not represent a PEF study and is not PEF compliant in multiple methodological choices.

The calculations of the environmental impacts of the solutions are based on generic assumptions and scenarios, of which the following pose the largest limitations:

- Average European (non-country specific) electricity mixes are used for the calculations. As energy shows to be one of the largest contributors within the life cycle, and environmental footprint of mixes of different countries may vary significantly, one shall be cautious with interpretation of the results, and consider the country- or company-specific mixes in comparison to average European
- The models assume generic processes in manufacturing and processing steps. One shall take into account that process characteristics and impacts may differ significantly between different facilities, industries, etc.
- All end of life scenarios for was are assumed to be waste incineration with energy recovery.

The results are calculated in two indicators: carbon footprint, and PEF score. While carbon footprint is only informative, the scoring of the solution is based on the PEF score:

Score 5: the PEF score with the solution implemented, is 40 or more percent lower than the PEF score of the baseline

Score 4: the PEF score with the solution implemented, is 25 to 40 percent lower than the PEF score of the baseline

Score 3: the PEF score with the solution implemented, is 10 to 25 percent lower than the PEF score of the baseline

Score 2: the PEF score with the solution implemented, is up to 10 percent lower than the PEF score of the baseline

Score 1: the PEF score with the solution implemented, is higher than the PEF score of the baseline

Circularity&Materiality

Circularity indicator is calculated as a share of the product that becomes available for the secondary market in the end of life (w/w). This indicator is dependant on the recyclability of the recovered substrate, share of the substrate in the product per se, and losses of the material in the recovery operations. Recyclability of materials is defined on expert judgement of potential situations. Note, that special recovery operations might be necessary to facilitate recovery and recycling in case of absent infrastructure.

The value is additionally adjusted on quality degradation coefficient. Quality degradation for recycling is defined based on the results of experiments within the project, as well as by the analogy of material. Quality degradation coefficient in case of downcycling is calculated as $0.5 \cdot Q_r$, where Q_r is the quality degradation coefficient in recycling.

Scoring is defined as follows:

Score 5: the circularity coefficient is between 0.8 and 1

Score 4: the circularity coefficient is between 0.6 and 0.8

Score 3: the circularity coefficient is between 0.4 and 0.6

Score 2: the circularity coefficient is between 0.2 and 0.4

Score 1: the circularity coefficient is between 0 and 0.2

The section Circularity & Materials provide as well information on the amount of waste avoided to go to final treatment. The indicator is informative only and is not included into the scoring. The amount of avoided waste is calculated as the total mass of the waste generated in the baseline scenario over the life cycle, minus the amount of waste generated in the applied DECOAT scenario over the life cycle.

Business and Economics

The business and economics score is assessed at the level of operational costs and revenues only. This is due to the fact that economic performance of each business case depends significantly on various factors and can drastically change depending on the geography, markets, scales, environment and facilities, etc. The calculations are based on generic market data and assumptions at the moment of the tool development, and shall be taken with caution.

Scoring is defined as follows:

Score 5: Operational costs of implementation of the DECOAT solution (over all involved life cycles) are more than 15% lower than the benefits of the substrate recovery

Score 4: Operational costs of implementation of the DECOAT solution (over all involved life cycles) are 10 to 15% lower than the benefits of the substrate recovery

Score 3: Operational costs of implementation of the DECOAT solution (over all involved life cycles) are 5 to 10% lower than the benefits of the substrate recovery

Score 5: Operational costs of implementation of the DECOAT solution (over all involved life cycles) are approximately equal to the benefits of the substrate recovery (+/- 5%)

Score 5: Operational costs of implementation of the DECOAT solution (over all involved life cycles) are more than 5% higher than the benefits of the substrate recovery

Safety

The safety score estimates the developed solutions from the standpoints of Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) and Chemical safety (CS). The provided information concerns the processes and substances involved in the implementation of the debonding solutions.

The overall safety score is taking a simple average of the scores of the solutions in OHS and CS.

Scoring for OHS as assessed as OHS risks of the processes added to the life cycle of the product with introduction of the DECOAT solution. Identified hazards are evaluated by OHS and technology experts on severity and probability, and the estimations are translated into a score from 0 to 1. For each of the added processes, the risk score is calculated as the maximum of all risks. For the solution overall, the risk score is calculated as the average of the process risks. The OHS score is calculated as 1 minus the total risk score.

Scoring for CS is calculated based on the information provided by the technology owners about the chemical compositions, and relevant registrations of the substances. Each of the criteria is assigned an importance weight by a chemical safety expert, and the received answers are registered binary (0 or 1). The total score is calculated as a weighted average.

Scoring is defined as follows:

Score 5: total safety score above 0.9

Score 5: total safety score from 0.7 to 0.9

Score 5: total safety score from 0.5 to 0.7

Score 5: total safety score from 0.3 to 0.5

Score 1: total safety score from 0 to 0.3

Overall score

The overall score is calculated as the weighted average of the scores in the five eco-design dimensions. The weights were identified in an expert survey.

For more information on the methodology, please inquire to [Natalia.chebaeva\[at\]ecomatters.nl](mailto:Natalia.chebaeva@ecomatters.nl)